

INVERSE MODELLING OF COMPRESSION MOULDING OF SMC WITH USAGE OF COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS

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SUMMARY: The purpose of this work is to investigate whether an inverse modelling approach by proportional regularisation can be applied to mimic the pressure distribution during compression moulding of SMC. The process is simulated with Computational Fluid Dynamics and the mastered parameter, the viscosity of the SMC, is allowed to vary as a function of time. A grid refinement study of two ways to model the process and for three fictitious pressure scenarios yields that the suggested approach work very well and that the numerical errors can be minimised as desired. Finally a validation process is carried out showing that to get quantitative agreements of the whole pressure field more advanced viscosity models must be used.

KEYWORDS: Inverse modelling, SMC, Compression moulding, CFD, Rheology.

INTRODUCTION

When manufacturing fibre composites by compression moulding processes such as Sheet Moulding Compound (SMC) a mixture of fibres, chalk, unsaturated resin and gas bubbles is forced to fill a mould. The resulting multi-phase flow is affected by variations in viscosity that is due to steep temperature gradients, a variable cure cycle and flow induced fibre orientation, Vahlund [1]. Hence several mechanisms are active during the process and the full set of governing equations does not have trivial solutions [2]. Thus the physical behaviour is multifaceted with phenomena such as squish, flow and boiling, Odenberger [3]. Although simplified models have shown to be efficient in some cases when predicting flow front positions, for instance, there is really a lack of models for accurate predictions of fibre orientation and void formation and transport. While uncontrolled fibre orientation may result in uneven strength and stiffness in a finished part, residual voids may appear on the surface as flaws and great efforts must be spent on minimising the number of them. This is certainly important in the automotive industries since their applications often must have a class A appearance. The required models can be obtained in a variety of ways, e.g. micromechanical modelling and experiments. We will here present an alternative route namely inverse modelling technique that can be used as one component to obtain the final void distribution.

Voids may form as well during the forming of the SMC as during the compression stage by different kinds of mechanisms. It is to start with well known that the SMC contains voids that either have been entrained into the polyester during mixing or created during the impregnation of the fibres. Besides, air can be entrapped at the flow front during the pressing stage. Hence by, as

a first approach, assuming that these voids are located in the SMC methods to remove them must be found in order to minimize the risk of surface flaws. In principal, the voids can be transported out of the SMC or dissolve into it, mechanisms that are strongly related to the spatial distribution of the pressure [4,5]. It is even so that if the pressure is too low at a specific temperature voids may form by boiling, of styrene, for instance [3]. Hence, it is obvious that the pressure distribution must be known. This quantity is in its turn directly related to the distribution in viscosity.

According to Tarantola [6] the scientific procedure for studying a physical system can be divided into three stages. In the *parameterization* stage a set of model parameters are chosen that, in an appropriate fashion, can describe the system. Then to discover the physical laws that allow for prediction of some measurable parameter, a *forward modelling* stage is suggested. In a final stage some measurements are set to influence the model parameters, *inverse modelling*. The advantage of studying the final stage combined with the first stage is manifolded, [7]. One is that uncertain model parameters can be tuned to best fit the experiments. Then it is possible to make predictions of parameters such as pressures and pressure gradients even with model simplifications. Such simplifications are sometimes necessary since the computer capacity is still not enough for the very complex real in-mould flow described above [1,2,3]. It is also stated by Tarantola [6] that success in one stage often leads to success in another stage. The inverse modelling is also a widely used technique in areas such as solid mechanics [8,9]. And since the technique with inverse modeling is the same for any continuum, solid as well as fluid, such work is giving synergy effects. Hence this leads to a very good start and one could expect the same benefits in this fluid mechanic approach that is presented by Kajberg and Westman [8,9].

The outline of this paper is as follows, a theoretical analysis is carried out so that the simulations performed can be verified. Then three model cases are defined that somewhat mimic a real moulding but where the pressure versus time curves are simpler. These relationships are implemented in a numerical model which in principal can be of two types: One-phase flow with an adaptive mesh or two-dimensional flow through a semi-stationary mesh. Both these models are verified by theory while the trust in the actual simulations is increased by grid refinement studies combined with the well known and widely used Richardson's extrapolation method [10]. Finally the method is compared to the experiments and the results obtained are discussed and some conclusions are presented.

THEORY

Of interest is a disc of a Newtonian liquid having a radius a that is placed between two parallel plates being a distance h apart. Then let the upper plates move towards the lower one at a constant speed and study the resulting flow. By continuity:

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = 0 \tag{1}$$

a then becomes a direct function of h according to:

$$a = \sqrt{a_0^2 \frac{h_0}{h}} \tag{2}$$

where the zeros indicate initial values. The evaluation in height of the disc may in its turn simply be described by the following relationship:

$$h = h_0 - \frac{dh}{dt} \quad . \quad (3)$$

Now when the disc is allowed to move towards the plane the velocity profile, at each r , may be assumed to take the following form:

$$u_r = -\frac{G(r)}{2\mu} z(h-z) \quad (4)$$

if transient effects, axial flow and flow front phenomenon can be neglected. Here G is the pressure gradient, μ the viscosity and r and z the spatial co-ordinates along the radius and perpendicular to the disc, respectively. Continuity now yields that:

$$G(r) = \frac{6\mu r}{h^3} \frac{dh}{dt} \quad (5)$$

By setting the pressure to p_0 at the flow front which is located at a the following pressure distribution results:

$$p(r) = p_0 + \frac{3\mu}{h^3} \frac{dh}{dt} (a^2 - r^2) \quad (6)$$

By the assumptions made this equation gives the pressure distribution in the disc at an arbitrary time or flow front position.

NUMERICAL PROCEDURE

All computations were done with the commercial software CFX4.4 which solves the flow in geometries modeled with structural elements. The computations were carried out with a high order upwind differencing scheme using double precision and the AMG multi-grid solver. The geometry in focus for the simulations was generated in a cylindrical coordinate system (x, r, α) and by applying axisymmetric conditions in the direction of α , see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Axisymmetric flow domain.

Solid walls are set as boundary conditions on high and low x while atmospheric pressure is set on high r . To drive the flow the upper solid wall is allowed to move at a velocity of 15 mm/s according to proper production conditions in the press. Now two techniques are used to simulate the pressing. To start with a one-phase fluid model with a full remeshing procedure is applied by usage of continuity and by assuming that the flow front moves as a plug, cf. theory. The numerical model uses the Eulerian description and solves for a plate with the same dimensions as in the analytical solution. Thus there are two moving boundaries, high x and high r . The way of treating these moving boundaries is to remesh in every time step. The domain is solved for three grids 4000, 1000 and 250 element, Secondly a two phase flow model is used where a Newtonian liquid displaces a gas (air). This numerical model also uses the Eulerian description. It is a two phase description that is based on a homogeneous model, which means that the two phases are sharing the same velocity field, and are continuous. The domain is as well in this case solved for three grids 2400, 600 and 150 elements. The initial charge is placed in the domain by setting its volume fraction to 1.0 and the other phase to 0.0. The only moving grid boundary is the high x moving wall and thus the remeshing is only carried out in the x -direction. This way of solving the problem is not the same as in the analytical case since the flow front will not move as a plug. The practical model difference is that the charge is only placed at the initial condition and not at each time step as in the other two cases. Hence if the real flow front behavior can be captured, this way of modeling better act as the real physics. It will however turn out that the numerical treatment of the liquid-gas interface at the solid walls strongly influences the results. The calculations are solved for each phase as described above for approximately 44 time steps where each time step is 0.01 s. And in order to investigate the quality and trust of the simulations and to find a grid independent solutions Richardson's extrapolation is used [10].

INVERSE MODELING

The main aim with this modeling is to be able to predict the pressure and pressure gradients accurately during pressing in any geometry. To be able to do that the viscosity as a function of time and spatial co-ordinate needs to be known. This is important since from a fluid dynamic point of view, the viscosity is the parameter that relates deformation rate to stresses in the fluid and hence the pressure. One methodology is thus to measure the pressure and temperatures in simple geometries but in several points and then find the viscosity distribution that match these pressures by inverse modeling. With a good enough viscosity model it is then likely that the flow in more complex geometries can be found. To demonstrate the model the viscosity is assumed to be constant and is solely fitted to pressure measurements in one spatial co-ordinate, the center of the disc. Once proven to work for this case it is only a matter of hard work for making it function for a general case. The viscosity is altered with the aid of the CFX4.4 specified FORTRAN subroutine USRVIS and by using the following proportional regularization expression

$$\mu_{new} = \mu_{old} - 2 \cdot (p_{calculated} - p_{experiment}). \quad (13)$$

This seemingly simple expression will first be tested for three bogus scenarios for the mid-point pressure during a radial flow pressing. These scenarios are i) a half sinus curve with a maximum of 16.5 MPa, ii) a ramped step up to the same value iii) and a step function also with a maximum of 16.5 MPa. Then the method will be applied to one real measurement performed enabling a comparison to pressure measurements performed at other locations.

RESULTS

Verification

In order to reveal how good approximation the numerical model is, the one phase model presented above is compared to the corresponding analytical expression, cf. Eqn. 6. It is seen that the numerical solution produce accurate and reliable result even for the coarsest grid, but the extrapolated value by Richardson's extrapolation is closest to the analytical solution as the pressing proceeds.

Figure 2. Left: Pressure presented for three grids where $4h = 250$ cells, $2h = 1000$ cells and $h = 4000$ cells. The analytical and Richardson's extrapolated curve is also included. Right: Error between analytically and numerically derived pressures.

For the two-phase formulation the discrepancy from the analytical solutions is, as expected, much larger, see Figure 4. This is probably not only due to the different geometries at the flow front but also a result of numerical problems at the contact lines formed between the liquid, gas and solids. The lagging of these contact lines is much larger than what is physically reasonable, see Figure 3, and it is not possible to extrapolate the pressure by Richardson's extrapolation, since the error tends to increase. Thus it is not possible to get a grid independent solution in this case. Hence this more physically correct model must be further developed before any conclusions on its usefulness can be made.

Figure 3. Volume fraction presented with cusp formation. Here red denote the solid phase and blue the gas phase.

Figure 4. Left: Pressure presented for three grids $4h=250$ cells, $2h=1000$ cells and $h=4000$ cells. The analytical solution is also included.
 Right: Error between analytically and numerically derived pressures.

Inverse modeling

An inherent effect of the inverse modeling is that at least one extra iteration cycle is brought into the simulation procedure. Hence, it is of interesting to scrutinize the convergence for as well the governing variables as the adapted ones here represented by the pressure and the viscosity, respectively. This convergence study is evaluated for the first time-step for the constant pressure case, 16.5 MPa by setting the initial viscosity to 0.25 MPas, initial pressure to 0.1 MPa and initial velocity to zero. Setting unreasonable values on these parameters will affect the result. A total of 2500 iterations were carried out but as shown in Figure 5 about 800 iterations will produce 1 % error of magnitude for the pressure and not much happens after 1500 hundred iterations. Hence, this is the maximum number of iterations that will be used henceforth. Please also notice that the first 50 iterations are dismissed since the errors are large during these initial steps.

Figure 5. Left: Pressure error defined as the difference between experimental value and calculated value. Right: Viscosity alterations for the same interval.

The next thing to do is to derive the error as a function of flow front position or equivalently time. This is done first for the constant pressure case 16.5 MPa. In the initial phase of the compression this error is relatively large but it soon decreases as the process continues. The maximum value calculated is also dependent on the grid and is 2.1 % for 250 cells, 1.6% for

1000 cells and 0.2% for 4000 cells, see Figure 6. Interestingly with the finest mesh the maximum error is relatively small also for 500 iterations, 3.1%.

Figure 6. Left: The error between experimental and calculated pressure for 500 iterations presented. Right: Corresponding plot but for 1500 iterations.

The corresponding viscosity curves for the constant pressure, presented above, are here presented cf. Figure 7.

Figure 7. Corresponding viscosity curve for the constant pressure 165 bar case.

Since the sinus formed pressure curve and step formed pressure curve is producing the same accuracy and result, as in the constant pressure case, it seems to be possible to minimize the error down to almost machine accuracy since the proportional regularization will not stop until a desired number of iterations are reached.

Validation

As a final activity the method verified above is validated with an experiment carried out with a fjellman 310 tons press and under production like conditions. During pressing the pressure were captured with two Kistler pressure transducer (6153C) located in the center of a plate to plate mould and at a distance of 37.5 mm from the center, respectively. The mould closing speed is set to 15 mm/s but in reality it ends up with a mean value of 8 mm/s, off course the velocity profile is measured and implemented in the simulation. The charge contains 5 layers of circular sheets with a diameter of 10 cm on top of each other with the height measured to 13 mm.

The Pressure curves are here presented, Figure 12, for the real case scenario. It can be seen that when using the Newtonian model as constitutive relation the shear thinning behavior of SMC is exclusive, notice that a constant viscosity is set trough the whole domain. There are two pressures included first the center pressure, presented as C, second the pressure at from the center, presented as P1. When comparing the results from the simulation and experiment it is obvious that the trend with increasing pressure in point P1 are there, although the simulated pressure evaluation is more flat.

Figure 12. Experimental center pressure (C-exp), calculated center pressure (C-sim), experimental pressure (C-p1) located a distance 37.5 mm from center and corresponding calculated pressure (P1-sim) presented.

Since it has been seen that the pressure are not stable and have large variations a statistical pressure, maybe median or mean value, based on several shoots, would be the right experimental input to the numerical model. Then the correlation for the pressure in P1 could be even better, or a more sophisticated material model could be developed. This is a hot burning topic for the future to reveal. Thus the procedure is as follows for a real case scenario based on several shoots:

- Measure pressures at different spatial locations.
- Simultaneous measure the true mould closing speed.
- Choose an appropriate constitutive model.
- Set up an inverse model calculation with the measurements, revealing the viscosity, and based on the constitutive model.
- Validate in some other experimental set-up.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The inverse modeling with a proportional regularization for the viscosity is producing results of which any desired error can be achieved. The cost for small errors is the number of iterations needed leading to long calculation times.

The initial values should be carefully investigated before a complete run including many time steps is carried out.

This method will be developed to include more complex material models as shear thinning material ones. Thus the true SMC behavior could be investigated.

More experiments must be carried out in order to get statistical value since every pressure curve is unique producing small oscillations.

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